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EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON FLEXIBILITY AMONG ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to determine the Effect of yogic practices on flexibility among Annamalai University students 20 subjects were selected from ‘Annamalai University’, chidambaram students were selected. They were selected randomly and their age group was between 15 to 30 years. Single group formed. All are in Experimental group. The experimental group participated in yogic practice training and for 6 weeks. The data were collected in the beginning and at the end. The training schedule was prepared systemically. The significance was tested at 0.05 levels.

Keywords: Yogic Practices; Students; Physical; Mental & Scientific System.

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1. Introduction

Yoga is a scientific system of physical and mental practices that originated in India more than three thousand years ago. Its purpose is to help each one of us achieve our highest potential and to experience enduring health and happiness. With Yoga, we can extend our healthy, productive years far beyond the accepted norm and, at the same time, improve the quality of our lives. The branch of Yoga that forms the main focus of my teaching work with both adults and children is called Hatha Yoga.

Hatha Yoga begins by working with the body on a structural level, helping to align the vertebrae, increase flexibility, and strengthen muscles and connective tissue. At the same time, internal organs are toned and rejuvenated; the epidermal, digestive, lymphatic, cardiovascular, and pulmonary systems are purified of toxins and waste matter; the nervous and endocrine systems are balanced and toned; and brain cells are nourished and stimulated. The end result is increased mental clarity, emotional stability, and a greater sense of overall well-being. Yoga is a form of exercise based on the belief that the body and breath intimately connected with the mind. By

controlling the breath and holding the body in steady poses, or asana, yoga creates harmony. Yoga is means of balancing and harmonizing the body, mind and emotion and is a tool that allows us to withdraw from the chaos of the world and find a quite space within.

2. Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to find out the Effect of yogic practices on Flexibility among Annamalai university students.

3. Methodology

For the purpose of the study 20 students were selected randomly from Annamalai university students and their age group was between 18- 30 years were selected. Single group formed. All are in Experimental Group. The experimental group participated in yogic practices for 6 week there is no control group. The data were collected in the beginning and at the end. The training schedule was prepared systemically. The significance was tested at 0.05 levels.

Administration of test

Flexibility

Equipment

The below figure shows the equipment to measure the v- sit and reach test.it will need sale, inch tape, pencil, marker. Flexibility was measured with V-Sit and Reach test.

Description

The subject responses are scored. In addition, the results are tabulated. The flexibility of the pre and post test scores of experimental group have been analyzed and presented in the below. The table shows the scores of the v-sit and reach test.

Scoring

The total score for a subject ranges from 11 to 23. The individual interpretation can be done through V-sit and reach flexibility Norms and proceeds and percentiles (%ile).

Interpretation

Female:

Age : Under 30

>14 very poor
15-16 poor
17-19 average
20-21 above average
22 good
<23 excellent

Male:

Age : under 30

>11 very poor
12-13 poor
14-17 average
18-19 above average
21 good
<22 excellent

Training protocol

The experimental group under went training that consist of preparatory practice and loosening practice and seven asana practice session, in a week 5 days for 6 weeks. In the morning, yogic training administrated from Monday to Friday respectively.

Training Format

Name of the asana	Duration of asana
ASANAS Stretching practices	5 minutes
Loosening practices	5minutes
Suryanamaskara	5 rounds
Padmasana Pawanamukthasana	2 times in each, 4 minutes
Trikonasana Padahastasana	4 times in each, 6 minutes
Pachimothasana Makrasana	4 times in each, 8 min
Kabalapathi, bastrika	5 minutes
Deep relaxation technique	20 minutes

Experimental Design and Statistical Procedure

The experimental group design used in this study was random group design involved ten subjects were included both male and female. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used for computing. Analysis of variance on flexibility of yogic practice group through v-sit and reach test is tabulated in table 1 and graphically represented in figure-1.

**Mean and standard deviations on flexibility among Annamalai University students
T-Test****Paired Samples Statistics**

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 VAR00001	15.8889	27	7.62250	1.46695
VAR00002	18.3704	27	7.20656	1.38690

Paired Samples Correlations

	N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1 VAR00001 & VAR00002	27	.910	.000

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 VAR00001 VAR00002	-2.48148	3.17890	.61178	-3.73901	-1.22395	-4.056	26	.000

The flexibility of the pre and post test scores of experimental group have been analyzed and presented in the below Table I.

It is clear from Table 1 that there is a significant improvement in Annamalai university students on flexibility, as $t (df 26) = 4.670, p < 0.05$. the standard deviation of pretest is 7.622 and the post test of standard deviation is 1.38690. It also clearly shows that flexibility increased from 15.889 to 18.370 cm through yogic practices and recorded 10.05% increase (MD – 2.48148 cm). It is interpreted that yogic practice showed significant increase 10.05% in flexibility for students.

The below graphical representation of the pretest and posttest of flexibility mean and standard deviation of annamalai university students.

Figure 1: Changes in flexibility from pre to post on Annamalai University students

4. Conclusion

The result of the study shows there is significant difference between yogic practice group on flexibility. Moreover, the result of the study shows that there is significant improvement in flexibility compared to pre -test.

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